

BAHA SI STEMOT I NEGOVATA PRI MENA

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Rezime

Lu|eto { to imaat o{ teten sluh nosat slu{ ni pomagala za da go kompenzi raat toj nedosti g. I ma edna druga kategorija od lica so o{ teten sluh koi poradi speci f i ~nosta na ni vnoto o{ tetuvawe, ne se vo sostojba da gi koristat zadu{ ni te slu{ ni aparati (hroni ~ni infekcii na uvoto, hol esteatom). Zatoa, za licata so takvi o{ tetuvawa se koristi zadu{ no pomagal o proteza, vgradeno hiru{ ki vo mastooid nata koska, kade { to zvukot preku koskata se prenesuva do kohleata. Toa e BAHAZvu ~ni ot procesor, proizvod na ENTI - FI K Medi kal si stem.

Kako rabot i BAHAsist emot

Prof. Brenemark pri negovoto istra ` u wawe prona{ ol na ~in kako da go upotrebi ~ isti ot ti tani um kako osnoven del za protetska rekonstrukcija, vku ~uvajki eden nov vid slu{ no pomagal o. Fiksaturata e vgradena vo koskata. Ova e opi { ano kako direktno strukturno i f unkcional no povrzuvawe me|u koskata i povr{ inata za i mplantot. BAHAsistemot e koskeno i ntegriran i mplant i istovremeno e ponuda za alternativen metod na povrzuvawe na zvukot prku ~erepot. Negovata f unkcija ne e da go zgol emuva ili reproducira zvukot, tuku da pomogne za prirodni ot zvuk ef ekti vno da dopatuva do kohleata.

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BAHA SYSTEM AND ITS USE

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Abstract

People with impaired hearing wear hearing aids to compensate that failure. There is one category of persons with impaired hearing that are not able to use behind-the ear hearing aids (chronical ear infections, cholesteatoma). People with that kind of damage use behind-the ear hearing aids-prosthesis that are implanted by surgery in the mastoide bone, where the sound is transmitted to the cochlea. That is the BAHAsound processor, product of ENTIFIK Medical system.

How does BAHASystem work

Prof. Brenemark during his research, found a way of using pure titanium as an anchoring unit and support for variety of prosthetic reconstructions including what was then a new type of hearing device. The fixture is incorporated within bone. This he described as direct structural and functional connection between living bone and the surface of a load carrying implant. The BAHASystem is an osseointegrated implant that offers an alternative method of conducting sound via the skull bone. Its function is not to magnify or reproduce sound, but rather, to help the natural sound one hears travel efficiently to functioning cochlea.

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Toa e samo implantiran tretman { to raboti niz di rektno koskeno povrzuvawe. Zatoa Baha-sistemot e edinstvena izvonedna možnost za re{ avawe na konduktivnata i me{ anata zaguba na slu{ noto o{ tetuvawe.

Za kog e namenet Baha sistemot

Baha-sistemot se upotrebuva kako aparat za lu|e so hroni ~ni infekcii na u{ ite, kade { to slu{ ni ot kontinui tet e o{ teten, kako kaj otosklerozata, travmata, hroni ~ni ot otitis, hroni ~ni te infekcii na u{ ite, kongenitalnata zaguba na sluhot, Tri ~er Kolinno-sindrom, steknate drugi malformacii na srednoto ili nadvove{ noto uvo { to rezultiral o so nedostig ili so nekompletno (sli ~en kanal-atresija) i kaj ednostrana gluvost. Baha-sistemot e sostaven od slu{ en procesor so mala titaniumska fiksatura, implantirana hi ru{ ki zad uvoto. Sistemot go prima zvukot i go povrzuva, go prenesuva niz koskata do srednoto uvo, proces poznat kako DBC-di rektno koskeno povrzuvawe { to zna-i deka vibracii te od zvu-ni ot procesor se prenesuvaat preku koskata do kohl eata.

It is the only implantet treatment that work through direct bone conduction. The Baha System is a unique and predictable solution for conductive and mixed loss hearing impairment.

How can use Baha SYSTEM

Baha system is used to aid people with chronic ear infections where hearing continued to deteriorate, post cholesteatoma surgery, trauma, otosclerosis, congenital hearing loss, Treacher Collins Syndrom or other acquired malformation of the middle or external ear resulting in a missing or incomplete, complete ear canal (atresia) and SSD - single sided deafness. The Baha System combines a sound processor with a small titanium fixture implanted behind the ear. The system allows sound to be conducted through the bone rather than via the middle ear - a process known as direct bone conduction. DBC - direct bone conduction process means that vibrations from the sound processor are transmitted via the bone to the cochlea.

Baha-sistemot se vgraduva so hi ru{ ka intervencija { to se izveduva za 45 - 60 minuti. Vo pove}eto slu ~ai taa se izveduva pod lokalna anestezija, so smestuvawe mala titaniumska fiksatura vo mastoidnata koska zad uvoto.

The Baha System is implanted by surgery that lasts 45 - 60 minutes under local anesthesia by putting a small titanium fixture in the mastoid bone behind the ear.

Po operaciji zvo~ni ot procesor se mesi po 10 do 12 nedeli. Pred operativno evluacija na kandidate za BAHA-sistemot vkl u-va kompletno medicinsko ispituvawe i iscrpna audiometriška evluacija. BAHA-sistemot se vgraduva od petgodi { na voznost i postari. Za pacienti pod petgodi { na voznost se prepore~uva BAHA@Softband. Ima slu~aj koga BAHA-sistemot e vgraden na dete od samo pet mesece so obostrana kanalna atrezija. Cena na BAHA-sistemot iznesuwa 2.200 USD { to go pravi sistemot dostapen do luleto koi od nego ima potreba.

Vo SAD od 1996 godi na BAHA-sistemot od FDA (Ministerstvo za lekovi i hrana) e prifaten kako tretman za konduktivno i me{ano gubawe na sluhot.

Vo 1999 BAHA-sistemot e odobren od FDA za pediatriski tretman kaj deca od pet godini i postari.

Vo 2002 godi na od FDA e odobren kako tretman za unilateralno senzorni neuralno gubawe na sluhot.

Prakti~ki aspekti

BAHA-zvo~ni ot procesor mo`e da se nosi pri sitem normalni aktivnosti, kako i druge slu{ni aparati. Toj se vadi koga se spie, pri kapawe ili vodeni sportovi, do deka specialna za{tita e potrebna pri kontaktni sportovi. BAHA-sistemot e dizajniran kako kompatibilen so celularni telefon.

The sound processor is being put 10 to 12 weeks after the surgery. The BAHA System is implanted from the age of 5 and older. BAHA@Softband is recommended for patient under the age of 5. There is a case when the BAHA System is implanted to a 5 months old baby with a bilateral canal ear atresia. The price of the BAHA System is 2.200 USA dollars that makes the system available to the people that have a need of it. Preoperative evaluation of the BAHA system candidate includes a complete medical history and a comprehensive audiometric evaluation.

In the USA since 1996 this has been accepted like a treatment for a conductive and mixed hearing loss by the FDA - Food and Drug Administration.

In 1999 BAHA System is approved by the FDA for pediatric use for children of age 5 and older.

In 2002 BAHA System is approved by the FDA for treatment of unilateral sensorineural hearing loss.

Practical aspects

The BAHA sound processor can be worn for all normal activities as any other hearing aid. It should be taken off when sleeping, in the shower and water sports, special protection is needed during contact sports.

BAHA system is designed to be compatible with cellular telephones.

Koga se upotrebuva telefon se drži blizu bez da se dopira BAHÁ-zvučni ot procesor.

BAHA-sistemot može da se upotrebuva so FM-služni sistemi i so infared sistemi te.

When telephones are used, the telephone receiver must be held close to (without touching) the BAHÁ sound processor. BAHÁ-system can be used with FM systems and infrared systems.

Vidovi BAHÁ - sistemi

Types of BAHÁ - systems

1. BAHÁ - klasik 300

1. BAHÁ - Classic 300

Audiološki indikatori:

BAHA-klasi k 300 odgovara za pacienti so ož tetena koskena sprovdli vost do 45 db. na 0.5; 1; 2 i 4 kHz

Adiological Indicators:

The classic 300 is suitable for patient with a pure tone average bone conduction threshold of the indicated ear better than or equal to 45 db at 0.5; 1; 2 and 4 kHz.

Baterii tip: 675 od 1.4 volti

Gol emi na na procesorot: 34 h 22 h 10

Težinata: 14 grama, vključno s baterijata.

Boja na procesorot: može da se najde vo 5 boji - crna, siva, olta, siva i boja na kōa. Pridružni delovi: zaštitno kapače, baterija, čistilna četka.

Battery type 675

Size 34 x 22 x 10

Weight 14 gr. including battery.

Colours: black, beige, grey, yellow and blue - sound processor, abutment cover, battery, cleaning brush.

2. BAHA - kompakt

Audiološki indikaciji:

BAHA-kompaktot e pogodan za pacienti so prag na ~i st ton na koskenata sprovodljivost, za indikacija na 45 db. na izmeren sluh na sledni ve frekrencii: 0,5; 1; 2 i 4 kHz.

BAHA-kompaktot e pomal od Klasi k 300. Toj e di zajni ran za da napravi kompresija, da go limi tira oš tetuvaweto i da go podobri kvalitetot na zvukot vo glasna sredi na.

Mo` e da se nabavi vo tri boi: crna, si va i be` (boja na ko` a).

Baterii: tip 13.

Gol emi na: 30 h 17 h 10.

Te` ina: 11 gr. vku~uvaj}i ja i baterijata.

2. BAHA - Compact

Audiological Indicators:

The Compact is suitable for patients with a pure tone average bone conduction threshold of the indicated ear better than or equal to 45 dB measured at 0.5; 1; 2 and 4 kHz

BAHA Compact is smaller then the Classic 300 and is designed with output compression to limit distortion and improve sound quality in loud environments.

It is available in the three colours: black, beige and grey.

Battery type: 13

Size: 30x17x10 mm

Weight: 11 d. including battery.

3. BAHA - kordelle 2

3. BAHA - Cordelle II

Audiološki indikacijski:

Kordel e 2 se prepora-va za pacienti { to imaat koskena o{ tetenost od 70 db, na sledni te frekenci 0.5; 1; 2 i 4 kHz

Transducerot, isto taka, ima mo`nost za izbor na tri boi: crna, siva i be` (ko`a boja), dodeka delot { to se nosi na pojas e so crna boja.

Baterii tip: 9 V za delot { to se nosi na teloto.

Golemina: 90 h 34 h 26.

Te`ina: 88 grama, vklju~uvajki ja i baterijata.

Te`ina na zadu{ni ot del: 20 gr.

Zaklu~ok

BAHA-sistemi te vo momentov pretstavuvaat re{eni e za lu|eto, osobeno za decata so karakteristi~ni o{ tetuvawa na sluhot koi ne mo`e da gi koristat standardni te slu{ni pomagala - kanalni, intrakanalni. Istovremeno BAHA-sistemot e so izrazi to poniska cena od Kohlearni ot implantat. Negovata primena e od osobeno zna~ewe kaj decata od predu~ili{na i u~ili{na vozast koi ne mo`e da gi koristat standardni te slu{ni aparati i koi se sre}avaat so problemi vo izgradba na govorot i glasot.

Literatura /References

1. Publication Entific Medical System-Bone Anchored Applications 1; 2004.
2. Shanker V, Davison T, Johanson I Newcastle BAHA Programme, Freeman Hospital, Newcastle, UK, 2004; 7.

Audiological Indicators:

The Cordelle II is recommended for patients who have average bone threshold of up to approximately 70 dB, measured at 0.5; 1; 2 and 4 kHz.

The transducer is available in three colours: black, beige and gray and the body worn unit is black.

Battery type 9V Body worn unit

Size 90 x 34 x 26

Weight: 88 g. including battery Transducer.

Weight: 20 gr.

Conclusion

BAHA Systems are solution for a lot of people especially children with characteristical hearing impairment that can't use standard hearing aids.

BAHA System has lower price then Cochlear implant. His use is significant for children from preschool and school age who can't use standard hearing aids and have problem their voice and language.

3. Audiology Online, BAHA-Implantable Hearing System, 2004.
4. Edition Quality Standards in BAHA for Children and Young People, National Deaf Children's Society (NDCS) UK 2003.